

Explanation

Express your opinion on the statements by stretching the string of the correct color to the correct next post:

Disagree
(Left)

Neutral
(middle)

Agree
(Right)

**Ready? Go to the next
Statement and start at the
pole where you left off!**

Statement 1

Picture this: Aisha is a doctor and uses artificial intelligence to detect skin cancer from photos of patients' skin. This allows her to detect skin cancer faster. However, it turns out that the program is more likely to overlook skin cancer in patients with darker skin tones than in those with lighter skin tones.

Statement: because it benefits some people, it's good that Aisha is using this program.

Span the string with the correct color to the next pole!

Statement 2

Picture this: With a new update, cars now use artificial intelligence to automatically brake for crossing pedestrians. This update greatly reduces the overall number of accidents involving pedestrians. But among people over 80, it actually causes more accidents.

Statement: Because the update generally causes fewer accidents, it is a good idea to use it.

Span the string with the correct color to the next pole!

Statement 3

Picture this: artificial intelligence is used in a nursing home to talk to lonely residents. Unfortunately, this program can only speak Dutch and not Frisian.

Statement: It is not justified for this program to be used in the nursing home. Thus, the Frisian residents will feel even more lonely.

Span the string with the correct color to the next pole!

**Span the last wire to
complete the network.**

**Anything else you want to
say? Feel free to leave your
opinion on the message
board!**